

Superconducting Wind Turbine Generator

Loïc Quéval (CentraleSupélec, Paris-Saclay University, loic.queval@centralesupelec.fr)
Markus Bauer (thyssenkrupp Transrapid, markus.bauer2@thyssenkrupp.com)

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Abstract

The increasing global demand for electricity has led to the exploration of innovative solutions such as offshore wind energy. Superconducting wind turbine generators offer a promising approach to address the challenges of conventional technologies, leveraging their technical advantages, techno-economic competitiveness, and geopolitical considerations in the quest for advanced, sustainable wind energy solutions. The EcoSwing project has already showcased the viability of superconducting technology through successful prototype deployment. However, the industrialisation of these generators faces challenges, including the need for further investment and the development of novel business cases. Overcoming these hurdles holds the potential to contribute to the global transition towards clean and sustainable energy sources.

Introduction

The increasing global demand for electricity, as projected by the IEA Stated Policies Scenario, presents a significant challenge. In 2018, the world's electricity generation stood at 26,603 TWh/year, with an estimated rise to 41,373 TWh/year by 2040 [1]. To address this, offshore wind energy has emerged as a promising solution. With a technical potential exceeding 120,000 GW, offshore wind has the capacity to generate over 420,000 TWh of electricity annually, which is more than enough to meet 11 times the global electricity demand in 2040 [2]. Shallow water sites, characterised by depths below 60 meters and favourable conditions for fixed-bottom foundations, offer a technical potential of over 87,000 TWh per year,

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surpassing global electricity demand twice over. Although deep water sites, ranging from 60 to 2,000 meters and requiring floating platforms, pose higher deployment costs, they offer a remarkable technical potential of over 330,000 TWh per year. The motivation for the large-scale deployment of wind energy stems from its abundant resources, the commitment to reduce greenhouse gas emissions, energy security concerns, the uncertain nature of fossil fuel prices, and the existing economic competitiveness of offshore energy, such as the Dunkirk offshore wind farm producing electricity at 44 €/MWh.

Solution

Technological advancements in wind turbine design have resulted in significant increases in turbine size, specifically in terms of tip height and swept area. This progress has led to a notable rise in the maximum power output of wind turbines. Over the years, the tip height of commercially available turbines has seen a remarkable growth, surpassing 100 meters in 2010 for a 3 MW turbine and exceeding 250 meters in 2021 for a 12 MW turbine. Presently, the Vestas V236-15.0 MW and the Siemens Gamesa SG 14-236 DD are among the world's largest wind turbines [3], [4]. Ongoing research and development efforts are focused on pushing the boundaries further with the goal of achieving 20 MW offshore wind turbines. The larger swept area of these turbines allows for a greater capture of wind, resulting in improved efficiency and a reduction in the cost of energy (LCOE).

Superconducting wind turbine generators make use of superconducting materials that exhibit zero electrical resistance at cryogenic temperatures. This innovative approach leverages the high current density of these materials to enable the development of smaller and lighter generators capable of achieving higher unit power output. Such solution can be attractive for three reasons:

- **#1 - Technical reason:** The development of superconducting wind turbine generators is being explored due to the challenges posed by conventional technologies in meeting the size and weight constraints. Due to their high reliability, direct drive drivetrains are preferred for offshore wind turbines. However, the mass of the generators increases with the power output and reaches several hundred tons at 15 MW output with simultaneously high requirements on permissible mechanical tolerances. A solution with lower mass is already of high interest for today's power level and will be even more important for the next generation of turbines with 20 MW and more particularly those intended for installation on offshore floating platforms.
- **#2 - Techno-economic reason:** Superconducting machines in wind energy conversion systems have the potential to offer greater competitiveness compared to conventional machines [5]. While it is true that the cost of high-temperature superconducting (HTS) wire and cooling equipment is still high, the lower weight of the superconducting generator has a positive impact on the entire wind energy conversion system, encompassing bearings, tower and (floating) platform as well as the installation effort.
- **#3 - Geopolitical reason:** The development of superconducting wind turbine generators gains importance due to geopolitical considerations. The European

Commission's Critical Raw Materials Act aims to enhance the European Union's self-reliance in the extraction, processing, and recycling of 34 critical metals and minerals, including rare earths [6]. Within the wind generator supply chain, the raw materials stage poses the highest risks. Presently, the EU provides only 1% of the raw materials required for wind energy production. Concerns are centered around the supply of rare earths, particularly for the production of permanent magnets, a key component of wind turbine generators, where China holds a quasi-monopolistic role. In this context, Europe must seek alternatives to permanent magnets, and superconducting generators emerge as a potential solution.

Possible impact in the framework of energy transition:

- The integration of superconducting technology in offshore wind energy systems can significantly contribute to the global energy transition by increasing the utilisation of clean, renewable energy sources and reducing the greenhouse gas emissions
- The enhanced efficiency and cost-effectiveness of large power wind turbines with superconducting generators without the necessity to source permanent magnets can help accelerate the deployment of offshore wind energy on a large scale.

Status

In the field of superconducting wind turbine generators, numerous industrial and academic projects have emerged. These projects encompass both partially superconducting machines [7], where only the rotor utilises high-temperature superconducting (HTS) windings, and fully superconducting machines [8], where both the rotor and stator incorporate HTS windings. In addition to conventional machines, such as field wound synchronous machines (EESM), more innovative topologies have also been considered [9].

In the United States, the Department of Energy (DOE) selected General Electric (GE) in January 2021 to receive funding of up to \$20.3 million. This financial support aims to facilitate the construction and testing of a scaled prototype of GE's generator concept on a wind turbine, showcasing advancements in the field.

In Korea, the E-cluster project has set its sights on developing fundamental technology for a floating offshore wind power platform, centered around a 10 MW HTS wind turbine generator.

In Europe, notable projects include INNWIND.EU, which has conducted studies on 10 to 20 MW machines and estimated the levelised cost of energy (LCOE) for various alternatives, including HTS machines, permanent magnet machines, and magnetic gearboxes. The SUPRApower project focused on designing a 10 MW direct-drive wind turbine with hardware testing of one pole coil. The Windspeed project concentrated on the design of a 3.5 MW direct-drive machine. Additionally, the EolSupra20 project [10], led by the University of Paris-Saclay, is conducting a feasibility study for a 20 MW fully superconducting wind turbine generator

utilising magnesium diboride (MgB₂) superconducting technology. But the most advanced project in terms of milestones is EcoSwing.

Figure: GC-1 wind turbine in Thyboron, Denmark, with the EcoSwing generator installed.

The EcoSwing project [11], [12] was a significant undertaking aimed at designing, developing, and manufacturing a full-scale multi-megawatt superconducting generator. The project, funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 program, sought to demonstrate the feasibility and advantages of using a superconducting drive train in wind turbines. From 2015 to 2019, the project team focused on replacing the existing permanent magnet (PM) synchronous generator of a modern wind turbine (3.6 MW, 14 rpm, 128-meter rotor), with a partially superconducting field wound synchronous machine. The EcoSwing generator exhibited a reduced size, with the diameter shrinking from 5.4 meters (PM generator) to 4 meters (HTS generator). Additionally, there was a 25% reduction in weight compared to the previous generator. It was estimated that a commercial design based on these findings could achieve a weight reduction of up to 40% when compared to a PM generator. To validate the performance and reliability of the EcoSwing generator, it underwent comprehensive testing. Initially, it was installed at the Institute of Wind Energy Systems (IWES) in Bremerhaven, Germany, for ground testing. Subsequently, the generator was mounted on an Envision GC-1 wind turbine in Thyboron, Denmark, for field testing. During field testing, the EcoSwing generator reached a

power output of 3 MW, the cryogenics system proved stable and reliable over a span of seven months, enabling the superconducting coil to demonstrate exceptional performance. The achievements of the EcoSwing project have demonstrated the viability of superconducting technology in wind turbines, advancing the project to Technology Readiness Level (TRL) 6-7 [11]. This milestone signifies the successful testing of a demonstration system operating in its operational environment at pre-commercial scale. The project's accomplishments have paved the way for future developments in the field of superconducting wind turbine generators, bringing the technology closer to widespread implementation and commercialisation.

Superconducting wind turbines are currently in the laboratory development phase, with ongoing research and innovation efforts. A significant milestone was achieved with the EcoSwing project, which marked the world's first high-temperature superconducting (HTS) wind turbine in 2019. However, despite these advancements, there are currently no pilot projects or industrial-scale deployment of superconducting wind turbines.

Challenges

The industry is looking towards the future, where conventional wind turbines have reached capacities beyond 15 MW. As the quest for higher power output continues, the business case for superconducting wind turbines needs to be re-examined. Technical considerations, such as the potential for 20 MW turbines, drive the motivation for further exploration. Challenges identified, including conductor length and cooling system limitations, are being actively addressed and resolved, further propelling the progress towards practical implementation of superconducting wind turbines.

Additionally, techno-economic assessments, particularly evaluating the levelised cost of energy (LCOE) for the entire system, are crucial in determining the feasibility and commercial viability of superconducting wind turbines.

Furthermore, a key aspect influencing the development of HTS machines for wind turbines is the critical raw material act, which addresses concerns related to rare earth materials. As the industry seeks to reduce its dependence on these materials, the development of fully HTS machines could enable power levels above 20 MW for fixed and floating offshore wind turbines.

The main challenge now is to introduce a new technology into an environment that demands the highest levels of reliability, such as offshore wind power. Although superconducting coils have already proved their reliability in many different applications, and cryogenic cooling systems are now available off the shelf, a superconducting generator the size of the one in question has not yet been built. To overcome this obstacle, a joint effort between a wind farm operator, an experienced wind turbine developer and experts in superconducting machines, supported by public funding, could be a realistic approach.

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References

- [1] IEA, "World Energy Outlook 2019," Licence: CC BY 4.0. [Online]. Available: <https://www.iea.org/reports/world-energy-outlook-2019>
- [2] IEA, "Offshore Wind Outlook 2019," Licence: CC BY 4.0. [Online]. Available: <https://www.iea.org/reports/offshore-wind-outlook-2019>
- [3] Vestas, "V236-15.0 MW Offshore Wind Turbine." [Online]. Available: <https://www.vestas.com/en/energy-solutions/offshore-wind-turbines/V236-15MW>
- [4] Siemens Gamesa, "SG14-236 DD Offshore Wind Turbine." [Online]. Available: <https://www.siemensgamesa.com/global/en/home/products-and-services/offshore/wind-turbine-sg-14-236-dd.html>
- [5] T.-K. Hoang, L. Queval, L. Vido, and D.-Q. Nguyen, "Levelized Cost of Energy Comparison Between Permanent Magnet and Superconducting Wind Generators for Various Nominal Power," *IEEE Transactions on Applied Superconductivity*, vol. 32, no. 7, pp. 1–6, Oct. 2022, doi: 10.1109/TASC.2022.3181996.
- [6] European Commission, S. Bobba, S. Carrara, J. Huisman, F. Mathieux, and C. Pavel, *Critical raw materials for strategic technologies and sectors in the EU – A foresight study*. Publications Office, 2020. doi: <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2873/58081>.
- [7] A. B. Abrahamsen *et al.*, "Superconducting wind turbine generators," *Supercond Sci Technol*, vol. 23, no. 3, p. 034019, Mar. 2010, doi: 10.1088/0953-2048/23/3/034019.
- [8] Y. Terao, M. Sekino, and H. Ohsaki, "Electromagnetic Design of 10 MW Class Fully Superconducting Wind Turbine Generators," *IEEE Transactions on Applied Superconductivity*, vol. 22, no. 3, pp. 5201904–5201904, Jun. 2012, doi: 10.1109/TASC.2011.2177628.
- [9] H. Ohsaki, Y. Terao, and M. Sekino, "Wind turbine generators using superconducting coils and bulks," *J Phys Conf Ser*, vol. 234, no. 3, p. 032043, Jun. 2010, doi: 10.1088/1742-6596/234/3/032043.
- [10] T.-K. Hoang, L. Queval, C. Berriaud, and L. Vido, "Design of a 20-MW Fully Superconducting Wind Turbine Generator to Minimize the Levelized Cost of Energy," *IEEE Transactions on Applied Superconductivity*, vol. 28, no. 4, pp. 1–5, Jun. 2018, doi: 10.1109/TASC.2018.2810309.
- [11] M. Bauer, "Superconducting generators for wind power, EcoSwing generator and outlook," in *COST ACTION 19108 Hi-SCALE 1st joint WG3/WG4 Industry-Academia Workshop on Applications for HTS Technologies in the Electrical Energy Chain*, Online, 2021.
- [12] X. Song *et al.*, "Commissioning of the World's First Full-Scale MW-Class Superconducting Generator on a Direct Drive Wind Turbine," *IEEE Transactions on Energy Conversion*, vol. 35, no. 3, pp. 1697–1704, Sep. 2020, doi: 10.1109/TEC.2020.2982897.